

penetrated the entire column were counted 7 d after planting and root penetration percentage calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Roots (no.) penetrating entire soil column}}{\text{Seeds (no.) planted}}$$

The length of the longest root for each plant and the dry weight of the entire root system in a core were measured.

There were significant differences in root dry weight among soil bulk density levels for each soil texture level (see table). Root length also differed except at the highest bulk density. Both root

Mean root performance at different soil bulk densities and textures. Peradeniya, Sri Lanka.

Soil bulk density (Mg/m ³)	Texture	Root dry weight (mg)	Root length (cm)	Root penetration ^a (%)
1.15	Soil	20	62	30 a
1.15	Soil + sand	13	45	25 ab
1.30	Soil	30	68	20 abc
1.30	Soil + sand	16	41	18 abc
1.45	Soil	11	4 a	0 d
1.45	Soil + sand	10	4 a	0 d

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

dry weight and root length increased up to soil bulk density of 1.30 Mg/m³, then decreased. Root penetration decreased

with increasing soil bulk density. The addition of sand significantly decreased both root dry weight and root length. □

Poultry manure as a N source for wetland rice

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Organic N is mineralized relatively slowly under anaerobic soil conditions. We studied whether poultry manure can be used efficiently as a source of N for wetland rice.

Soil of the experimental field was a Fatehpur loam sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.27% organic C, and 0.04% total N. Poultry manure (C:N 12, 1.85% N, 1.81% P) was compared with urea at 0, 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Poultry manure was incorporated into the soil in the last puddling; urea was applied in 3 equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting rice PR 106.

After the rice was harvested, soil samples were tested for organic C and available P, and wheat was grown to study the residual effect. On half of each plot, P at 0 and 26 kg/ha was applied. A uniform 80 kg N/ha as urea was applied overall.

A quadratic grain yield response of rice to urea up to 180 kg N/ha was observed (see figure). When the source of N was poultry manure, the response was linear up to 180 kg N/ha; it was

Rice grain yield response to application of N through urea and poultry manure in Ludhiana, India.

Residual effect on wheat of poultry manure applied to rice in Ludhiana, India.

	Urea or poultry manure applied to rice as kg N/ha			
	0	60 kg	120 kg	180 kg
<i>Soil organic C (%)</i>				
Urea	0.27	0.28	0.28	0.29
Poultry manure	0.27	0.29	0.28	0.30
LSD (P=0.05)			0.02	
<i>Olsen's available P (kg/ha)</i>				
Urea	7.5	9.9	8.7	8.7
Poultry manure	7.5	10.8	14.2	12.8
LSD (P=0.05)			2.2	
<i>Wheat yield (t/ha) with P applied to poultry manure-amended plots</i>				
No P	2.95	3.33	3.49	3.63
26 kg P/ha	3.55	3.68	3.70	3.77
LSD (P=0.05)			0.19	

significantly less than to urea at 60 and 120 kg N/ha. Poultry manure at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha produced rice grain yield equivalent to that by 37, 96, and 168 kg urea N/ha, respectively. On the basis of N uptake, poultry manure N was 80% as efficient as urea N at all rates of application.

Urea and manure differ in increasing

rice grain yield at 60 kg N/ha, perhaps because at low application rates, sufficient manure N might not be mineralized for critical growth stages of rice. No significant differences in uptake of P and K by rice were observed between urea and poultry manure.

A residual effect of poultry manure N was shown by wheat grown after rice

only at the highest rate of application (see table). The residual effect of the manure in supplying P to wheat was conspicuous, both through Olsen's available P and a significant response of wheat to 26 kg P/ha in plots where poultry manure had been applied to rice at 0, 60, and 120 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen-fixing potential of blue-green algae (BGA) from Kerala ricefields

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We studied the effect of P and Mo on N fixation by a mixture of BGA in 1-liter beakers containing 200 g each of air-dried soil from Trichur district (pH 4.56, CEC 21 meq/100 g, C 3.2196, N 31%) brought to neutrality by adding calcium carbonate at 700 kg/ha. Two levels of Mo (0.2 and 0.4 ppm) and 2 levels of P (4 and 8 kg/ha) were used, in 9 treatments replicated 3 times.

BGA crust at 10 kg/ha was inoculated. The beakers were kept in the open for 3 wk with water level

Effect of Mo and P on N fixation^a by BGA in Kerala ricefields, India.

	N fixation ^b (kg/ha)			Mean
	No Mo (control)	0.2 ppm Mo	0.4 ppm Mo	
No P (control)	6.3	6.3	12.5	8.4
4 kg P/ha	12.5	15.7	9.4	12.5
8 kg P/ha	9.4	12.5	18.8	13.6
Mean	9.4	11.5	13.6	

^aTotal N after 3 wk - initial N. ^bCD (0.05) for comparison of Mo and P = 3.16.

Confidence limit for means = ± 2.109

CD (0.05) for comparison of combinations = 5.48

Confidence limit for cells = ± 3.653

maintained at 5-10 cm above soil level. Then the soil was allowed to dry and the BGA crust was incorporated. Total N was determined by the microKjeldahl method.

Both Mo and P had favorable influence on N fixation. The combination treatment 8 kg P/ha and

0.4 ppm Mo fixed the largest amount of N (see table). At 8 kg P/ha, each additional Mo level improved N fixation by BGA. On average, addition of 0.4 ppm Mo increased N fixation by 44% over the control; addition of 8 kg P/ha increased N fixation by 62% over the control. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Effect of an interim summer crop in a rice - wheat rotation

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During the summer (May-Jun) in the Punjab, a shortduration crop is grown between the dry and wet season main crops. This crop could be a cereal fodder, a pulse, or a green manure.

Green manuring is gaining importance with increasing costs of

fertilizers and threats of pollution. In rice, green manuring with sesbania has been successfully used to supplement fertilizer N. On the other hand, growing a cereal fodder might deplete available nutrients and adversely affect rice yield. We conducted a field experiment 1984-85 to study the effect of summer maize *Zea mays* fodder, mungbean *Phaseolus aureus* pulse, cowpea *Vigna sinensis*, sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea*, and sesbania *Sesbania aculeata* green manure (GM) crops on the following rice crop.

Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept), alkaline (pH 8.5), with 0.40% organic C, 7.5 kg available P/ha, and 81 kg available K/ha.

Crops were planted the first week of May. Maize was fertilized with 120 kg N/ha applied in 2 splits and harvested for fodder at 2 mo. Mature mungbean pods were picked. Mungbean residue and the 3 green manure crops were incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice. N was applied to rice at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha in 3 equal splits (1/3 at transplanting, 1/3 3 wk and 1/3 6 wk